

Identity, diversity and freedom of expression from the academy of Loja

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A few days ago, communication professors and researchers from the universities of La Rioja met to identify areas of collaboration. From the backgrounds of each team, they aspire to face challenges and take advantage of opportunities.

The academy is committed to sustained progress, and it is time to be together to respond to the urgencies of the country and the region, particularly from the sciences and practices of communication that advocate freedom of expression as a priority route to other rights.

There are conditions to contribute, from the Latin American School of Communication, to the global debates in the so-called knowledge society. The reflections of professors and students should not be figures, numbers that feed editorial businesses with the fruits of research financed with public funds, but rather services and well-being for communities.

There is another academy, open, tolerant and humane, which is concerned with knowing people first, their environments and limitations in harmony with nature. There is another university that fights for civic values, transparency, the common good and food sovereignty, among other purposes, to provide the keys to save the earth from catastrophes, and for these reflections to be present in the media agendas.

Calls to people's conscience to avoid wars, to respect cultures and creeds are not heard, they are silenced, it seems that diversities are of little importance. Thus, the future appears grey, literally.

In the face of what has been described above, the conjunction of wills is a hope to advance towards new pedagogical experiences, an effective social linkage and good science that promotes the presence and cultural contributions of Loja to the world.